

Report of the Scientific Committee of the Spanish Agency for Food Safety and Nutrition (AESAN) on the safe use of an aqueous solution of hydrogen peroxide, acetic acid and peracetic acid (23/17/15) as a processing aid for the bacterial disinfection of the washing water used for cut carrots and lettuces, peeled garlic, sweet potatoes, persimmons, mangoes and avocados in processing plants

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Abstract

The company Productos Citrosol S.A. has requested a safety assessment on the use of an aqueous solution containing hydrogen peroxide (23 %), acetic acid (17 %) and peracetic acid (15 %) as a processing aid. As stabilisers, 1-hydroxyethylidene-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP) (<0.2 %) and dipicolinic acid (DPA) (≤ 0.01 %) are included in the solution.

The proposed use of the processing aid is the bacterial disinfection of the washing water used for cut carrots and lettuces, peeled garlic, sweet potatoes, persimmons, mangoes and avocados in processing plants. By disinfecting the washing water, it can be employed for the consecutive washing of fruits and vegetables through a recirculation system, keeping the water in suitable conditions and reducing water consumption. The dosages requested are 0.07 % for cut carrots

and lettuces, 0.13 % for peeled garlic, 0.27 % for sweet potatoes and avocados, and 0.20 % for persimmons and mangoes.

Considering the worst-case scenario for the presence of residues and the consumption of lettuces, carrots, garlic, sweet potatoes, persimmons, mangoes and avocados in Europe, a daily intake has been estimated for the possible residue together with a consumer risk assessment, by calculating the margin of safety (MOS).

The Scientific Committee concludes that, based on the information provided by the applicant and taking into account the proposed composition and conditions of use, the use of the processing aid does not involve a health risk for the consumer.

Key words

Lettuces, carrots, garlic, sweet potatoes, persimmons, mangoes, avocados, processing aid, bacterial disinfection.

1. Introduction

The company Productos Citrosol S.A., located in Potrías (Valencia), has requested a safety assessment on the use of an aqueous solution of hydrogen peroxide (23 %), acetic acid (17 %) and peracetic acid (15 %) as a processing aid in the bacterial disinfection of water used for washing cut carrots and lettuces, peeled garlic, sweet potatoes, persimmons, mangoes and avocados on their arrival at the processing plants. The processing aid, manufactured by the company Solvay Chemicals International S.A. (Brussels, Belgium), is made from two active compounds: hydrogen peroxide and acetic acid in aqueous solution, resulting in the formation of a third active compound, peracetic acid, by means of chemical equilibrium. To maintain this equilibrium, the stabilisers 1-hydroxyethane-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP) (<0.2 %) and dipicolinic acid (DPA) (≤ 0.01 %) are used. This is the same aqueous solution as that previously assessed by the Scientific Committee of the AESAN in 2016 for use on citrus fruit and tomatoes (AESAN, 2016), and has a similar composition to another solution previously assessed in 2013 (AESAN, 2013).

In response to the application, the Management Board of the Spanish Agency for Food Safety and Nutrition (AESAN) has asked the Scientific Committee for a safety assessment of the use of said aqueous solution as a processing aid, considering the "Guidelines of the relevant documentation for the assessment of processing aids intended for use in human food" (AESAN, 2010).

As regards to the authorised uses of the components in human food, hydrogen peroxide is authorised in France as a processing aid in casings; acetic acid is a food additive authorised in the European Union (E 260) and peracetic acid is authorised as an additive or processing aid in countries including Canada and Australia. With regard to the stabilisers, HEDP is authorised as a processing aid or additive forming part of solutions for the disinfection of meat, vegetables and fruit in Australia and the United States, and DPA is found in a traditional Japanese fermented food.

As it is not possible to dismiss the presence of residues in the final products (fruit and vegetables) after the use of these aqueous solutions, in accordance with the criteria established in the aforementioned Guidelines, the processing aid is classified as in a situation 4: substance authorised in human food for which the ADI has not been established and the use of which may result in the technically unavoidable presence of residues. In line with this situation, the applicant for the product presents information relating to the following aspects:

- Administrative data and general overview.
- Physicochemical properties.
- Technological function.
- Analysis of residues: analytical method and validation of the method.
- Studies and data on safety: A Level.
- Study on consumption and evaluation of the expected level of consumer intake.

2. Administrative data and general introduction

2.1 Commercial name and composition

The product proposed as a processing aid with the commercial designation Citrocide Plus is an aqueous solution of hydrogen peroxide (23 %) and acetic acid (17 %) that maintains a chemical equilibrium

with peracetic acid (15 %) and water. To maintain this equilibrium, two additional stabilizers are used (1-Hydroxyethane-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP) (<0.2 %) and dipicolinic acid (DPA) (≤ 0.01 %)).

2.2 Intended use of the substance

Processing aid in the bacterial disinfection process of water used for washing cut lettuce and carrots, peeled garlic, sweet potatoes, persimmons, mangoes and avocados at processing plants.

2.3 Authorised uses in human food

Table 1 contains examples of authorised uses and assessments of these substances.

Table 1. Examples of authorised uses and assessments		
Substances	Authorised use/assessment	Country/Reference
Hydrogen peroxide	Regulation (EC) No. 853/2004 establishes a limit for hydrogen peroxide residue of 10 ppm for gelatine and collagen	European Union (EU, 2004)
	Favourable toxicological assessment as processing aid in the processing of blood derivatives and cephalopods	Spain (AESAN, 2011)
	Authorised for use as processing aid in tripe	France (Arrêté, 2006)
	Authorised for use in production of beer as a clarifying agent (maximum quantity 135 mg/kg) in buttermilk to discolour and maintain pH (100 mg/kg) and oat hulls as a bleaching agent (GMP)	Canada (DJC, 2019)
	Generally recognised as safe (GRAS) (21 CFR 184.1366), used in milk (0.05 %), whey (0.04 %), whey cheese coloured with annatto (0.05 %), starch (0.15 %), corn syrup (0.15 %), emulsifiers (1.25 %), dehydrated eggs, stomachs, beef trotters, herring, wine, tea and wine vinegar	United States (FDA, 2019a)
	Authorised in combination with acetic acid for the process of washing or peeling fruit and vegetable that are not unprocessed raw material and not exceeding 59 mg/kg in the washed solution	United States (FDA, 2019b)
	Authorised for use as processing aid (bleaching agent, washing and peeling, pH stabilizer and inhibitor) in several foods (5 mg/kg)	Australia (ANZFSC, 2019)
Acetic acid	Authorised as food additive (E 260) in accordance with Regulation (EC) No. 1333/2008, with maximum specific dose as <i>quantum satis</i>	European Union (EU, 2008)
Peracetic acid	Authorised for use as technological adjuvant of peracetic acid in solution with hydrogen peroxide and acetic acid, in egg shells destined for manufacture of <i>ille flotant</i> (solution at 2.5 % with 4.5 % of peracetic); in peas and green beans for sterilization (500 mg/l of peracetic acid); in starch, potato starch and derivatives (1 kg/tonne); in raw ready-to-eat salads (4th range); blanched spinach for freezing (75 mg/l pf peracetic) and wheat prior to milling (3 l of a solution based on 15 % peracetic and 23 % hydrogen peroxide per tonne of wheat)	France (Arrêté, 2006)

Table 1. Examples of authorised uses and assessments

Substances	Authorised use/assessment	Country/Reference
Peracetic acid	Authorised, in combination with acetic acid for the process of washing or peeling fruit and vegetable that are not unprocessed raw material and not exceeding 80 mg/kg in the washed solution	United States (FDA, 2019b)
	Authorised as a food additive (starch modifying agent)	Canada (DJC, 2019)
	Authorised as processing aid as bleaching agent, for washing and peeling and as a catalyst with maximum permitted level of 0.7 mg/kg	Australia (ANZFSC, 2019)
1-Hydroxyethane-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP)	Authorised together with peracetic acid for the process of washing or peeling fruit and vegetable that are not unprocessed raw material and not exceeding 4.8 mg/kg in the washed solution	United States (FDA, 2019b)
	Mixed peracetic acid additive authorised, acetic acid, hydrogen peroxide, peroxyoctanoic acid and HEDP as disinfectant for poultry carcasses, parts, tripe and organs with a maximum concentration of peroxyacids of 220 mg/kg as peracetic acid, 110 mg/kg of hydrogen peroxide and 13 mg/kg of HEDP	United States (FDA, 2019c)
	Toxicological assessment favourable for acetic acid solutions, peracetic acid, hydrogen peroxide and HEDP (may also include octanoic and peroxyoctanoic acid) for use in poultry carcasses and meat	(EFSA, 2014)
	Authorised for use as a processing aid in water and as a chelating agent in disinfectants for meat, fruit and vegetables	Australia (ANZFSC, 2019)
Dipicolinic acid (DPA)	Included in the database of Effective Food Contact Substance (FCS) Notifications comprised primarily of aqueous solutions together with acetic acid, peracetic acid, hydrogen peroxide and HEDP	United States (FDA, 2019d)
	Present in the spores of the bacteria <i>Bacillus subtilis</i> and found in great quantities in a traditional Japanese fermented food known as <i>natto</i> ¹ , a food which consists of fermented soy seeds	Japan (Ohsugi et al., 2005)

¹The average daily intake of dipicolinic acid (DPA) of the Japanese population from the food *natto* is 0.6-4 mg (Ohsugi and Sumi, 2011).

2.4 Acceptable Daily Intake

No ADI has been established for hydrogen peroxide, peracetic acid, DPA and HEDP as individual components (EFSA, 2019a) (JECFA, 2019a). With regard to acetic acid, it is authorised as a food additive (E 260) with a maximum specific dose as *quantum satis* (EU, 2008).

The Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives (JECFA) has established a non-specified ADI for antimicrobial solutions which may include hydrogen peroxide, acetic acid and peracetic acid, also including HEDP as a stabilizer (JECFA, 2019b). JECFA also considers that in the conditions of use for these solutions, the quantities of residue in treated foods do not pose a great concern from a food safety perspective (JECFA, 2004, 2005).

3. Physiochemical properties

3.1 Composition and detailed formulation

The product proposed as a processing aid is an aqueous solution of hydrogen peroxide (23 %) and acetic acid (17 %) that maintains a chemical equilibrium with peracetic acid (15 %) and water. As indicated in the application, together with active compounds, the product contains two stabilizers: 1-hydroxyethane-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP) (<0.2 %) and dipicolinic acid (DPA) (≤ 0.01 %). Table 2 shows the composition of the processing aid.

Component	Function	CAS No.	Molecular weight (g/mol)
Hydrogen peroxide	Active substance	7722-84-1	34
Acetic acid	Active substance	64-19-7	60.1
Peracetic acid	Active substance	79-21-0	76.1
1-Hydroxyethane-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP)	Stabilizer	2809-21-4	205.02
Dipicolinic acid (DPA)	Stabilizer	499-83-2	167.12
pH <1.5			

3.2 Product specifications

Table 3 shows the specifications and results of the analysis of four batches of the processing aid assessed.

Component	Specifications (% p/p)	Analysis certificates (% p/p)			
Hydrogen peroxide	21-24	22.5	22.3	22.5	22.5
Acetic acid	-	-	-	-	-
Peracetic acid	14.5-15.5	15	15.1	14.9	14.9
1-Hydroxyethane-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP)	<0.2%	0.164	0.172	0.179	0.155
Dipicolinic acid (DPA)	<0.01%	0.0034	0.0018	0.0097	0.0116

3.2.1 Product Stability

The applicant employs the same formula assessed in 2016, for which data were provided with the aim of demonstrating its stability at room temperature, with the loss of concentration of peracetic acid approximately 1 % p/p per year (AESAN, 2016).

3.2.2 Reactivity

As indicated in the 2016 report, the reactions that take place in water are decomposition of the compounds with peroxide groups producing acetic acid and water (EFSA, 2005, 2014) (AESAN, 2016).

JECFA, when evaluating disinfectant solutions that contain hydrogen peroxide, peracetic acid, octanoic acid, peroxyoctanoic acid and HEDP indicate that, in contact with foods, the active ingre-

dients decompose rapidly in non-toxic substances and the quantities of acetic and octanoic acid that may remain as a result of the decomposition of peracetic acid and the peroxyoctanoic, do not constitute a safety concern. It also states that hydrogen peroxide decomposes rapidly in contact with food, obtaining water and oxygen (JECFA, 2004, 2005).

Furthermore, the use of this type of solution does not seem to negatively affect the nutrient content (Vitamin C and β -carotene) present in fruit and vegetables (JECFA, 2006).

4. Technological function

4.1 Technological use claimed

The applicant claims that the technological use is as bacterial disinfectant of water used for washing cut lettuce and carrots, peeled garlic, sweet potatoes, persimmons, mangoes and avocados. The washing of fruit and vegetables takes place on arrival at processing plants with the aim of minimising contaminations or recontaminations during this phase of the process. It also allows for the reduction of water consumption at packing plants and prevents the emission of waste with a strong chemical contaminant load.

Other advantages indicated by the applicant, in addition to efficiency, are that it does not alter the quality and nutritional value of food treated and presents a very low phytotoxicity level.

4.2 Target foods or food group

Water used for washing cut lettuce and carrots, peeled garlic, sweet potatoes, persimmons, mangoes and avocados.

4.3 Level of use requested

According to the applicant, the dosages of processing aid to be used are those presented in table 4.

Product	Use dosage (% V/V)	Concentrations in washing solutions (mg/l)			
		Peracetic acid	Hydrogen peroxide	HEDP	DPA
Cut lettuce	0.07	100	153	1.33	0.07
Cut carrots	0.07	100	153	1.33	0.07
Peeled garlic	0.13	200	306	2.67	0.14
Sweet potatoes	0.27	400	612	5.32	0.28
Persimmons	0.20	300	459	4	0.21
Mangoes	0.20	300	459	4	0.21
Avocados	0.27	400	612	5.32	0.28

The maximum contact time of fruit and vegetables with washing solutions shall be 1 minute and these solutions shall be replaced daily. After washing, a final rinsing of the fruit and vegetables shall be performed using potable water.

4.4 Justification of use, interest and efficiency

As indicated in the reports of the Scientific Committee of 2013 and 2016 (AESAN, 2013, 2016), the first post-harvest treatment carried out with vegetable products is washing. The maintenance of the washing solution is fundamental as it recirculates, with residues from the chemical treatment applied to the crops previously, dirt from the harvest and spores and pathogenic organisms deposited on vegetable material passing to the solution. This leads to the accumulation of contamination increasing considerably on each recirculation. To prevent the washing solution from being converted into a vector of infection due to cross-contamination, it must be ensured that the microbiological quality is retained, using disinfectant products for that purpose provided that it is guaranteed that degradation products and residue of the antimicrobial agent used do not constitute a risk to the health of the consumer or the environment.

According to the indications of the applicant, in the case of minimally processed fruit and vegetables, this problem becomes even more relevant as some of these products are marketed as ready-to-eat which implies that the final consumer does not need to carry out any washing of the product in their home. At industrial level, if the washing process is completed exclusively using potable water from the network, this water will become contaminated quickly, reaching levels of microbiological contamination that would constitute a risk to the consumer. For this reason, the water must be continually replaced to reduce this risk, which would involve increased water consumption and a significant environmental impact.

The applicant highlights, as an advantage over the chlorine-based disinfectants commonly used in the sector (sodium hypochlorite and, to a lesser extent, chlorine dioxide or calcium hypochlorite), the absence of evidence in relation to the formation of potentially harmful derivatives like trihalomethanes (Monarca et al., 2002). In this regard, results of a trial carried out with minimally processed vegetables washed with different dosages of Citroside Plus (250, 375 and 500 ppm of peracetic acid) showed that the use of the technological adjuvant did not increase the concentration of trihalomethanes present in the water used.

It also indicates that the mixtures of peracetic acid/hydrogen peroxide are a type of disinfectant that presents one of the broadest spectres of activity, highly efficient in various ranges of pH and working temperatures, with the presence of organic material not being a limiting factor in said activity. By replacing the washing water daily, the possibility of accumulating residue of the processing aid components that are not degraded on the vegetable products undergoing washing is minimized.

4.4.1 Efficacy studies

The applicant provides the results of trials carried out on a pilot scale to establish the dosage of processing aid necessary to maintain the washing waters recirculating in adequate microbiological conditions for all the uses requested:

- In the case of lettuce and carrots, a trial was conducted in which they were inoculated with *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 (4.42-4.54 log UFC/ml) and subsequently washed for 45 seconds with washing solutions prepared with different dosages of the processing aid (250, 375 and

500 ppm of peracetic acid). The counts of *Escherichia coli* were inferior to the detection limit (1 UFC/ml) in all washing solutions analysed. Petri et al. (2015) also obtained counts of *Escherichia coli* O157:H7 below the detection level (1 UFC/ml) in washing solutions, in a trial in which the washing water for lettuce and carrots was inoculated with 9 log UFC/ml and subsequent washing was carried out with a processing aid solution (100 ppm of peracetic acid).

- For peeled garlic, baseline samples of the washing solutions were taken (freshly prepared solution) and after 1 or 2 hours of use for washing in the drum. The immersion time of peeled garlic was 1 minute and the washing solution was prepared by adding Citroside Plus to 0.13 % (200 ppm of peracetic acid). The counts of total mesophilic bacteria, enterobacteriaceae, moulds and lactic bacteria were below the detection limit in all the washing solutions analysed.
- In the case of sweet potatoes, immersion for 1 minute in the two washing solutions prepared with Citroside Plus at 0.20 % (300 ppm of peracetic acid) and at 0.27 % (400 ppm of peracetic acid). Baseline samples were taken (freshly prepared solution) and after successive washing of 10 pallets. The counts of total mesophilic bacteria, enterobacteriaceae, moulds and yeast were below the detection limit for the washing solution prepared with Citroside Plus at 0.27 %.
- For persimmons, a simulation was carried out in dynamic solution until 32 washing cycles were completed with two washing solutions prepared with Citroside Plus at 0.13 % (200 ppm peracetic acid) and 0.20 % (300 ppm of peracetic acid), respectively. In the case of samples of solution prepared with Citroside Plus at 0.20 %, the counts of total mesophilic bacteria were, in all cases, below the detection limit. For mangoes, a semi-industrial pilot trial was carried out, in which a growing dosage of Citroside Plus was added until an accumulated concentration of 400 ppm of peracetic acid was reached. The counts of total mesophilic bacteria, enterobacteriaceae, moulds and yeast were below the detection limit for the washing solution prepared with Citroside Plus at 0.20 % and 0.27 %.
- In the case of avocados, the results of a study carried out with a processing aid (used at 0.8 %, 400 ppm of peracetic acid) with the same components as the processing aid under study although to a lesser concentration. Baseline samples of the washing solutions were taken (freshly prepared solution) and after 1, 2, 3 and 4.5 hours of use for washing in the drum. The counts of total mesophilic bacteria, total coliforms, faecal coliforms and *Escherichia coli* were, in all cases, below the detection limit.
- In addition, the results of a trial carried out by an independent laboratory were provided, containing the microbiological parameters established in Royal Decree 140/2003 establishing the health criteria of water quality for human consumption (*Escherichia coli*, Enterococo and *Clostridium perfringens*) (BOE, 2003). To carry out the trial, Citroside Plus at 0.07 and 0.27 % was added to the water samples, obtaining, in all cases, counts below the detection limit (1 UFC/ml) from the first 30 seconds of contact.

With respect to phytotoxicity, the applicant presents the results of the trials carried out with some of the products in which the phytotoxicity thresholds are established.

4.5 Description of the process

4.5.1 Forms of incorporating processing aid

The incorporation of processing aid takes place during the washing of vegetable products on arrival at processing plants. In the case of lettuce, carrots and peeled garlic the washing system is used, consisting of a drum varying in size where the vegetables are first cut (or not, depending on the size) to be washed, subsequently proceeding with the final rinsing process with potable water through a system of pressure showers. The maximum time in the drum is 1 minute. Then, vegetables are spun to eliminate the highest possible quantity of water before packaging.

The washing of other vegetable products (avocados, sweet potatoes, persimmons and mangoes) can be carried out using immersion in the drum or pressure showers or jets over brushes, turning the fruit on a conveyor belt that feeds the fruit through a moving brush washer. In both cases, the maximum time for contact with the washing solution is 1 minute and after washing takes place with a final rinsing with potable water through showers.

The addition of the processing aid to the washing water in the drums or showers takes place using programmable automatic dispensers, using waves to measure the peracetic acid concentration and to maintain it at a constant level. These washing solutions are replaced in full daily.

4.5.2 Identification of phases of elimination of processing aid

In the case of active substances, it is expected that their presence in fruit and vegetable is negligible given that these substances decomposed rapidly, giving rise to acetic acid, water and oxygen.

With respect to stabilizers, in a form evaluated in 2013 with the same components but in different proportions, it was verified that HEDP not only accumulated but that, unlike DPA, it rapidly disintegrated with successive treatments. Moreover, it indicated that peracetic acid remained or diminished slightly in final treatment solutions for peppers and citrus fruits using continuous dosage, compensating for its degradation (AESAN, 2013).

DPA is accumulated in the washing solution using successive cycles. In this case, the washing solution is renewed daily and therefore it is expected that the level of dipicolinic acid residue in these matrices stay below the detection level in the evaluation carried out for citrus and tomatoes (AESAN, 2016).

Moreover, the applicant affirms that both the fruit and vegetables are subject to a final rinse with potable water before proceeding with commercialisation, preventing the possible presence of peracetic acid residue or the stabilizers in these foods. In addition, in the case of carrots and lettuce, after final rinsing with potable water are they undergo mechanical spinning for the purpose of eliminating the highest possible quantity of surface water.

5. Residue studies

As indicated in the 2016 report (AESAN, 2016), these types of solutions have undergone evaluation both on the part of JECFA and EFSA (European Food Safety Authority). In this study, JECFA has

carried out an evaluation of the antimicrobial solutions of peroxyacids that contain HEDP (<1 %), hydrogen peroxide (4-12 %), acetic acid (40-50 %) and octanoic acid (3-10 %) in balance with peracetic acid (12-15 %) and peracetic acid (1-4 %). JECFA considers that the small quantities of these peroxyacids in the foodstuffs at the time of consumption do not present a safety concern (JECFA, 2005).

On their side, EFSA (2005) assessed the use in poultry carcasses of a peroxyacid-based solution, comprised of peracetic acid (<15 %), peroxyoctanoic acid (<2 %) hydrogen peroxide (<10 %), acetic acid, octanoic acid and 1-hydroxyethane-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP), concluding that in the conditions of use described, they pose no safety concern. EFSA reached similar conclusions with respect to the safety of possible residues in a previous study (EFSA, 2014), where it also assessed the use, in poultry carcasses and meat, of solutions comprised of peracetic acid (12-20 %), hydrogen peroxide (6-10 %), acetic acid (35-45 %) and HEDP (0.1-<1 %). One of the solutions also contains octanoic acid (3.2 %) and peroxyoctanoic acid (1.4 %). The concentration of use of peracetic acid could vary according to the type of application, between 230 and 2000 ppm.

With regard to the processing aid subject to assessment, as indicated before, is classified within a situation 4: substance authorised in human food with no established ADI and use of which can lead to the presence of residues technically inevitable in accordance with "Guidelines of the relevant documentation for the assessment of processing aids intended for use in human food" (AESAN, 2010). Consequently, the applicant must present information on studies of residues (analytical method and validation method).

In this regard, the applicant presents the results of a study carried out for the determination peracetic acid residue, HEDP and DPA in the washing solutions for fruit and vegetables subject to the application. The study was carried out by the applicant in a pilot plant using a simulation in which organic material, suspended solids and a microbial load were used, with the aim of simulating the closest conditions to reality.

Samples of the washing solution for fruit and vegetables corresponding to three phases of the process were taken:

- Pre-treatment solution (cycle 0): sample taken once the processing aid is added to the washing water in the dosage requested for each fruit and vegetables and prior to commencing the washing process.
- Post-treatment solution (cycle 10): sample taken after 10 simulated washing cycles with contact time of the solution with fruit and vegetables of 1 minute.
- Post-rinsing water: sample taken after final rinsing with distilled water in the fruit and vegetable previously drained for 10 seconds.

The analyses of peracetic acid were carried out using an amperometric analyser (Table 5). With regard to HEDP and DPA, the analysis was conducted by an external laboratory contracted by the industry requesting the report via LC-MS/MS, with detection limits and quantification of 0.01 µg/l and 0.1 µg/l for HEDP (Table 6), and of 0.25 µg/l and 1 µg/l in the case of DPA (Table 7).

Table 5. Contents of peracetic acid (ppm) in the washing solutions and post-rinsing water

Samples	Pre-treatment solution	Post-treatment solution	Post-rinsing water
Cut lettuce	102	104	n.d.
Cut carrots	107	104	n.d.
Peeled garlic	202	201	n.d.
Whole sweet potatoes	407	400	n.d.
Whole avocado	408	406	n.d.
Whole mango	304	300	n.d.
Whole persimmon	308	290	n.d.

n.d.: not detected. Detection limit: 1 ppm.

Table 6. Contents of peracetic acid HEDP (mg/l) in the washing solutions and post-rinsing water

Samples	Pre-treatment solution	Post-treatment solution	Post-rinsing water
Cut lettuce	1.1191	2.6757	1.7176
Cut carrots	0.6122	1.7022	0.9177
Peeled garlic	1.3357	2.8356	1.3442
Whole sweet potatoes	4.5543	11.6080	0.2887
Whole avocado	5.3349	8.5232	2.2730
Whole mango	3.6371	6.8793	1.2105
Whole persimmon	3.7477	3.5599	1.3174

Table 7. Contents of DPA (mg/l) in the washing solutions and post-rinsing water

Samples	Pre-treatment solution	Post-treatment solution	Post-rinsing water
Cut lettuce	0.0720	0.1322	0.0760
Cut carrots	0.0687	0.1322	0.0834
Peeled garlic	0.1129	0.1799	0.0864
Whole sweet potatoes	0.2356	0.5581	0.0965
Whole avocado	0.3145	0.4665	0.1148
Whole mango	0.3060	0.5933	0.1393
Whole persimmon	0.3582	0.5707	0.1561

Unlike other studies (AESAN, 2013) carried out in the pilot plant with conditions for real use, this was carried out at a pilot plant through a simulation, HEDP does not degrade.

The estimation of the residue of the peracetic acid, HEDP and DPA present in the fruit and vegetables was conducted determining, by difference of weight, the water retained on each fruit and vegetable after the treatment with the solution and subsequently considering that all this water

retained evaporates leaving residues of HEDP and DPA on the fruit and vegetables. To carry out the estimation residues of HEDP and DPA, measured concentrations are used in the post-treatment solutions given that, in some cases, the concentrations in the post-treatment solutions are inferior to those expected (Table 8). It is therefore considered a worse scenario before possible variations in the dosage of processing aid.

In the case of peracetic acid, it is not detected in the post-rinsing waters and, as would be expected, its decomposition in acetic acid and water (EFSA, 2014).

Samples	HEDP	DPA
Cut lettuce	0.1579	0.0078
Cut carrots	0.1958	0.0152
Peeled garlic	0.0539	0.0034
Whole sweet potatoes	0.0929	0.0045
Whole avocado	0.0511	0.0028
Whole mango	0.0069	0.0006
Whole persimmon	0.0142	0.0023

6. Study and data relating to safety of DPA and HEDP

As indicated, there is no ADI established for DPA and HEDP. Similar to the procedure followed in 2016 for this same processing aid (AESAN, 2016), the risk assessment is based on the determination of the margin of safety (MOS), considering when the MOS is >100 there is no risk to the consumer. The MOS is calculated taking into account the no observed adverse effect level (NOAEL) and the estimated daily intake (EDI).

In this regard, EFSA (2009) assessed chromium and zinc picolinate as food supplements based on the calculation of the MOS, concluding that picolinate do not constitute a risk to the consumer. To do that, a NOAEL of 2100 mg/kg b.w./day was established for picolinic acid was established based on a study carried out on rats (NTP, 2008) (EFSA, 2009) and exposure due to the use of zinc picolinate (Zn) as the source of Zn was estimated at 1.57 mg picolinate/kg b.w./day. In the case of HEDP, a NOAEL of 50 mg/kg b.w./day was established based on the studies carried out using rats and rabbits (EFSA, 2014).

7. Study of consumption and evaluation of anticipated level of intake of DPA and HEDP by the consumer

To obtain the estimate for exposure, the European Union country with the highest consumption (mean and 95th percentile consumers only) for each product, both for adults and toddlers (aged 1 to 3), in accordance with the EFSA's Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database

(2019b) was selected. As additional criteria, data corresponding to a number of consumers <10 were not taken into account, except in cases where they were the only data available (persimmons in children). In the case of Spain, the consumption data was collected by ENALIA (*Encuesta Nacional de Alimentación en la población Infantil y Adolescente*) and ENALIA 2 (*Encuesta Nacional de Alimentación en población adulta, mayores y embarazadas*), both included in the Comprehensive European Food Consumption Database. In this regard, in the case of adults, higher consumption data were used for lettuce (Spanish data), carrots (Netherlands), garlic (Romania), sweet potatoes (France), avocados (Belgium), mangoes (Portugal) and persimmons (Estonia) (Tables 9-10); and in the case of toddlers (aged 1-3), the highest consumption levels were: lettuce (Holland), carrots (Finland), garlic (Estonia), sweet potatoes (Portugal), avocados (United Kingdom) mangoes (United Kingdom) and persimmons (Estonia) (Tables 11-12).

To obtain the estimated daily ingestion (EDI), estimated residues of DPA and HEDP were considered for each product (Table 8). The margins of safety (MOS) (Tables 9-12) are calculated based on the estimated daily intake and NOAELs (2100 mg DAP/kg b.w./day and 50 mg HEDP/kg b.w./day).

Table 9. Estimated exposure to DPA in adults and calculation of MOS

Product	Adults			
	Consumption (g/kg b.w./day)		EDI (mg DPA/kg b.w./day)	MOS
Lettuce	Mean	0.69	0.00000538	390 189 521
	P95	1.88	0.00001466	143 207 856
Carrots	Mean	0.66	0.00001003	209 330 144
	P95	1.85	0.00002812	74 679 943
Garlic	Mean	0.05	0.00000017	12 352 941 176
	P95	0.13	0.00000044	4 751 131 222
Sweet potatoes	Mean	0.87	0.00000392	536 398 467
	P95	1.66	0.00000747	281 124 498
Avocados	Mean	0.75	0.00000210	1 000 000 000
	P95	1.71	0.00000479	438 596 491
Mangoes	Mean	1.80	0.00000108	1 944 444 444
	P95*	3.80	0.00000228	921 052 632
Persimmons	Mean	1.36	0.00000313	671 355 499
	P95	3.01	0.00000692	303 336 704

*Includes mango, mango juice and mango juice drink.

Table 10. Estimated exposure to HEDP in adults and calculation of MOS

Product	Adults			
	Consumption (g/kg b.w./day)		EDI (mg HEDP/kg b.w./day)	MOS
Lettuce	Mean	0.69	0.000109	458 922
	P95	1.88	0.000297	168 434
Carrots	Mean	0.66	0.000129	386 913
	P95	1.85	0.000362	138 034
Garlic	Mean	0.05	0.000003	18 552 876
	P95	0.13	0.000007	7 135 721
Sweet potatoes	Mean	0.87	0.000081	618 636
	P95	1.66	0.000154	324 225
Avocados	Mean	0.75	0.000038	1 304 631
	P95	1.71	0.000087	572 207
Mangoes	Mean	1.80	0.000012	4 025 765
	P95*	3.80	0.000026	1 906 941
Persimmons	Mean	1.36	0.000019	2 589 064
	P95	3.01	0.000043	1 169 810

*Includes mango, mango juice and mango juice drink.

Table 11. Estimated exposure to DPA in toddlers and calculation of MOS

Product	Toddlers			
	Consumption (g/kg b.w./day)		EDI (mg DPA/kg b.w./day)	MOS
Lettuce	Mean	1.37	0.00001069	196 518 810
	P95	2.75	0.00002145	97 902 098
Carrots	Mean	2.60	0.00003952	53 137 652
	P95	6.58	0.00010002	20 996 641
Garlic	Mean	0.16	0.00000054	3 860 294 118
	P95	0.38	0.00000129	1 625 386 997
Sweet potatoes	Mean	2.00	0.00000900	233 333 333
	P95	4.43	0.00001994	105 342 363
Avocados	Mean	1.36	0.00000381	551 470 588
	P95	3.91	0.00001095	191 815 857
Mangoes	Mean	5.26	0.00000316	665 399 240
	P95*	13.71	0.00000823	255 288 111
Persimmons	Mean	4.15	0.00000955	220 010 477
	P95	6.81	0.00001566	134 073 932

*Includes mango, mango juice and mango juice drink.

Table 12. Estimated exposure to HEDP in toddlers and calculation of MOS

Product	Toddlers			
		Consumption (g/kg b.w./day)	EDI (mg HEDP/kg b.w./day)	MOS
Lettuce	Mean	1.37	0.000216	231 136
	P95	2.75	0.000434	115 148
Carrots	Mean	2.60	0.000509	98 216
	P95	6.58	0.001288	38 809
Garlic	Mean	0.16	0.000009	5 797 774
	P95	0.38	0.000020	2 441 168
Sweet potatoes	Mean	2.00	0.000186	269 107
	P95	4.43	0.000412	121 493
Avocados	Mean	1.36	0.000069	719 466
	P95	3.91	0.000200	250 249
Mangoes	Mean	5.26	0.000036	1 377 638
	P95*	13.71	0.000095	528 547
Persimmons	Mean	4.15	0.000059	848 464
	P95	6.81	0.000097	517 052

*Includes mango, mango juice and mango juice drink.

The high values obtained for the MOS (>>100) in all cases indicate that there is no risk to the consumer.

Conclusions of the Scientific Committee

The Scientific Committee, having assessed the application for the assessment of the safe use of an aqueous solution of hydrogen peroxide (23 %), acetic acid (17 %), peracetic acid (15 %), 1-hydroxyethane-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP) (<0.2 %) and dipicolinic acid (DPA) (≤0.01 %) as a processing aid in the bacterial disinfection of water used for washing cut carrots and lettuces, peeled garlic, sweet potatoes, persimmons, mangoes and avocados at the processing plants, concludes that, based on the information provided by the applicant, and considering the composition and conditions of use proposed, the use of the processing aid is not a health concern for the consumer.

The conclusions of this report refer exclusively to the solution under assessment as a processing aid under the conditions of use proposed and with the current composition, both as regards its active components and its stabilisers. They cannot be extrapolated to other formulae or conditions other than those assessed. It should be remembered that the kg of fruit and vegetables treated, the climatic conditions and the dirt may affect the concentrations of the components of the processing aid in the treatment mixes and therefore, in the possible residues.

This assessment does not imply an authorisation for use, nor does it affect uses other than as a processing aid in the process of the bacterial disinfection of the water used for washing cut carrots and lettuces, peeled garlic, sweet potatoes, persimmons, mangoes and avocados in processing plants. This use implies a final rinse with potable water, immediately after the application of the

washing water containing the processing aid, in order to eliminate the possible residues from the fruit and vegetables.

Products processed in this way must comply with all applicable food legislation and, once on the market, the food business operator must ensure the absence of contaminants, residues or undesirable microorganisms, or their presence below the maximum established limits.

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